

**glycan
trigger**

D2.3 – Identification of pathogenic gut bacteria favoured by host glycome alteration and with proinflammatory effects

WP2

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
BH	Benjamini-Hochberg
CD	Crohn's Disease
diff.btw	Difference between groups
EC	Enzyme Commission
FLASH	Fast Length Adjustment of SHort reads
FDR	False discovery rate
G1	CD patients with relapse after 6 months of surgery
G2	CD patients in remission after 6 months of surgery
IBD	Inflammatory Bowel Disease
LDA	Linear Discriminant Analysis
M0	Time of surgery
M6	Six months after surgery
MS	Mass spectrometry
PICRUST	Phylogenetic Investigation of Communities by Reconstruction of Unobserved States
UC	Ulcerative Colitis
UDP-GlcNAc	UDP-N-acetylglucosamine
UDP-ManNAc	UDP-N-acetylmannosamine

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About the project

GlycanTrigger is a project funded by the European Union, within the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions (RIA). The long-term goal of GlycanTrigger is to unlock a new checkpoint that regulates health to chronic inflammation transition by proposing mucosa glycans modifications as a master switch towards the early perturbation of host-microbial interactions and the consequent activation of both innate and humoral immune systems. Ultimately, we want to intercept or revert this master switch and thereby exploit/analyse whether this constitutes an opportunity to prevent the development of chronic inflammation in at-risk individuals.

Chronic inflammation is the underlying cause of numerous diseases, including Crohn's disease (CD), which may have a preclinical phase with immunological changes occurring before symptoms manifest. To improve disease prediction and prevention, our innovative approach seeks to understand the health-to-intestinal inflammation transition using CD as a disease model. The GlycanTrigger project will investigate when, why and how changes in glycosylation at the surface of the gut mucosa, constitute an early trigger of the health-to-inflammation transition. We will address how changes in glycosylation of the gut mucosa act as a primary event that dysregulates not only local mechanisms, but also systemic mechanisms associated with health to inflammation transition. Although high-risk/high-gain, our project is based on appropriate and long-standing expertise and fundamental biological principles that the consortium has helped establish and is thus likely to lead to (i) breakthrough biomedical concepts in the driving factors that trigger the health to chronic inflammation transition and to (ii) novel predictive tools for early detection of at-risk individuals to develop chronic inflammation, as well as to (iii) a novel intervention strategy that will be tested for disease prevention. In the longer term, the results of GlycanTrigger will improve health literacy through better-informed management of health status, diet and life-style to maintain a healthy gut. Our strategy for understanding the transition from health to gut inflammation is comprehensive and includes the impact of mucosa glycans on local and systemic mechanisms.

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 2.3 titled, *Identification of pathogenic gut bacteria favoured by host glycome alteration and with proinflammatory effects*, outlines the findings from Work Package 2 (WP2) of the GlycanTrigger project, integrating results from **Task 2.1, Mucosa glycosylation signature in CD patients in relation to microbial, metabolomic and immunological dynamics associated with gut inflammation**, and **Task 2.2, Changes in the host glycocalyx and the mechanistic impact on microbiome composition and microbial-derived metabolites during intestinal inflammation**. This deliverable explores the interplay between changes in mucosal glycome and its impact in intestinal microbiota composition associated with health to intestinal inflammation transition.

Analyses of patient samples revealed distinct associations between mucosa glycan features and selected microbial communities in individuals experiencing disease relapse compared to those in remission. Complementary experiments in mice further supported these findings, demonstrating that specific glycosylation changes can influence selected microbial profiles. Overall, these preliminary results suggest that host glycosylation plays an important role in shaping the composition and function of the gut microbiota associated with IBD development. These results provide further understanding of how early changes in the mucosal glycome may influence microbial dynamics linked to health to intestinal inflammation transition.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1. Introduction

Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD), comprising Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis (UC), represents a complex inflammatory disorder with a substantial global health impact.[1] Although its exact cause is still unknown, IBD is strongly linked to disruptions in the delicate balance between gut microbiota and immune regulation, often influenced by genetic factors.[2-4]

The intestinal environment is regulated by a tight dynamic between several players. Preserving homeostasis depends on a harmonious relationship among microbiota, immune responses, and barrier integrity. When this balance is lost, functional impairments occur, ultimately triggering intestinal inflammation.[5]

Glycosylation is a posttranslational modification that consists in the addition of glycans (carbohydrates) to the surface of cells, proteins and lipids. Alterations in this process, particularly at the level of the intestinal mucosa, have been associated with several diseases, such as IBD.[6, 7] Indeed, this process plays a critical role in T cell function and immune modulation within the gut. Nevertheless, its direct impact on intestinal microorganisms remains poorly understood. Glycans can serve as a carbon source for gut microbes,[8-10] and previous studies show that these can reshape the microbiome and reduce gut pathology in mice when administered as part of dietary interventions.[11]

On the other hand, the gut microbiota is shaped by its environment, including nutrient supply, immune activity, and physical and chemical conditions. In IBD, chronic inflammation changes these conditions, causing more oxidative stress, higher levels of reactive oxygen species, less iron, and limited carbohydrate availability.[12] These changes impose shifts in gut microbes, a pattern that is widely described in IBD large observational cohort studies.

A major question that remains unanswered is whether host mucosa glycosylation has the capacity to impact different microbial taxa in the gut, and if this can underlie the transition from health-to-intestinal inflammation. Despite dysbiosis is well reported in the context of IBD, how specific taxa are influenced by the glycan availability in the intestine and its impact in gut health is a ground-breaking topic that may directly boost new approaches to tackle IBD.

This project aims to investigate whether host glycosylation shape gut microbiota composition associated with recurrence and remission in human IBD and how this may act as a hallmark of the health-to-disease transition.

Chapter 2

Methods

2. Methods

2.1 Sample preparation and 16S rRNA sequencing

In this study, we used a well-established cohort of CD patients that underwent ileocecal resection (n=60) between 2017 and 2021 at Hôpital St Louis, Paris (POP-Remind cohort), with two distinct time points: at the time of surgery (M0; n=30); and 6 months after (M6), including one group with disease relapse (G1), and other composed by patients in remission (G2, n=30/each). A representative scheme of this cohort is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 The POP-REMIND cohort illustrating the longitudinal profile of mucosa-associated microbiota composition in relationship with mucosa glycolyx characterization in post-operative Crohn's disease (CD) patients.

The cohort consists of two groups of patients, each providing mucosa-associated microbiota samples and ileal mucosa glycome data. Samples were collected at two time points: before surgery (M0) and six months post-surgery. Group 1 (G1) includes 30 patients who experienced a relapse at M6, presenting an inflamed mucosa, while group 2 (G2) comprises 30 other patients, who recover at M6, presenting a non-inflamed mucosa.

2.2 16S rRNA sequencing

Intestinal tissue biopsies were collected, and then the gut microbiota composition was characterized by 16S rRNA sequencing. The data was integrated with the mucosal glycome characterization, previously generated in the group by mass spectrometry (MS). Sequencing was performed on an Illumina MiSeq platform (Illumina) at GenoScreen with a 250-bp paired-end sequencing protocol. Raw paired-end reads were subjected to quality filtering using the PRINSEQ-lite PERL script³⁴ by truncating the bases from the 3' end that did not exhibit a quality & less than 30 based on the Phred algorithm. Subsequently, we performed paired-end read assembly using FLASH (fast length adjustment of short reads to improve genome assemblies) with a minimum overlap of 30 bases and a 97% overlap identity. Finally, the search and removal of both forward and reverse primer sequences using CutAdapt was done, with no mismatches

allowed in the primers' sequences. Assembled sequences without forward and reverse primers were removed.

2.3 Prediction of the functional potential of the microbiota

We used Phylogenetic Investigation of Communities by Reconstruction of Unobserved States (PICRUST2) to predict the functional composition from 16S rRNA sequencing data. The glycosylation-associated pathways in the microbiota of CD and HC individuals were predicted based on Enzyme Commission (EC) and MetaCyc pathways.

2.4 Statistical Analysis of human IBD cohort data

2.4.1 Association between glycan traits and microbial communities

The association between each glycan trait and microbiota was assessed via logistic regression after adjusting for age, race and sex. Logistic regression was estimated for each time point before diagnosis separately. P-values from logistic regressions were adjusted for multiple comparisons via the BH method and to control de false discovery rate (FDR), and only markers with an adjusted P value smaller than 10% were reported as significant.

2.4.2 Coexpression network analysis

We performed coexpression network analysis to assess correlations between mucosal glycosylation profiles and microbiome composition for CD and healthy (HC) individuals. Permutation-based techniques were used to find associations significant at a false discovery rate of 5%.

2.5 Animals

C57BL/6 wild-type (*Mgat5^{WT}*) and *Mgat5*-deficient mice (*Mgat5^{-/-}*) were bred and maintained in accredited animal facilities at the Institute for Research and Innovation in Health (i3S). Mice were housed in groups of 5-10, in HEPA filter-bearing cages, under 12-hour light/dark cycles. Autoclaved chow and water were provided *ad libitum*. Females between 9 and 14 weeks were used. Experiments were conducted with the approval of the Animal Ethics Committee and the Animal Welfare Body of the i3S. The protocols are in agreement with in-house standards and rules for animal experimentation, comply with national legislation and are integrated within a project, which is licensed by the Portuguese competent authority – DGAV (license number 009268/2022-06-02).

2.6 16S rRNA sequencing, bioinformatic and statistical analysis of gut microbiota composition in mouse models

Mouse stools were collected and snap frozen in liquid nitrogen. Microbiota composition was determined by 16S rRNA gene sequencing and analysed as previously described.[13] Sequencing was performed on an Illumina MiSeq platform (Illumina) at GenoScreen with a 250-bp paired-end sequencing protocol. Raw paired-end reads were subjected to the following process: (1) quality filtering using the PRINSEQ-lite PERL script [14] by truncating the bases from the 3' end that did not exhibit a quality & less than 30 based on the Phred algorithm; (2) paired-end read assembly using FLASH with a minimum overlap of 30 bases and a 97% overlap identity; and (3) searching and removing both forward and reverse primer sequences using CutAdapt, with no mismatches allowed in the primers sequences. Assembled sequences without forward and reverse primers were removed. Joined sequences were imported into the amplicon version of Qiime2 (version 2023.9).[15] Sequence inference was performed using Deblur.[16] Taxonomy was assigned using the SILVA database (v138.1).[17]

Chapter 3

Results

3. Results

3.1 Correlation studies between intestinal microbiota composition and glycan traits in CD

In this task we aim to pinpoint specific connections between selected microbial taxa and glycan traits associated with the risk of recurrence vs remission in CD. To address this, we performed correlation analyses to explore how shifts in host glycome modulate gut microbiota in patients experiencing relapse (G1, inflamed mucosa) and remission (G2, non-inflamed mucosa) six months post-surgery (M6) (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Correlations between glycan traits and microbial families.

A. Associations between glycan traits and microbial families were assessed in relapse (G1) and remission (G2) samples from CD patients. **B, C.** Pearson's correlation of glycome-microbiome interactions; letters in graphs: A –

Proteobacteria species 1; B – Bacillota species 1; C – bacteroidota species 1; D – Glycan trait 1; E – Glycan trait 2; F – Glycan trait 3.

We identified significant associations between microbial families and specific glycan traits in both G1 and G2 groups. In relapse (G1), the abundance of a specific Proteobacteria species was positively correlated with glycan trait 1 in the gut mucosa. Concomitantly, Bacillota species 1 negatively correlated with glycan trait 3 (Pearson's coefficient=-0.70; Figure 2B). Our previous findings have shown that glycan trait 3 is associated with inflammation (G1), while glycan traits 1 and 2 are present in the mucosal glycoprofile of non-inflamed mucosa (G2).

Interestingly, in remission (G2), the correlation between Bacillota species and glycan trait 3 was no longer observed. Additionally, Bacteroidota species exhibited a positive correlation with glycan trait 2 (Pearson's coefficient=0.73; Figure 2C). Although patients in both G1 and G2 underwent surgery, the associations between glycan traits and the microbiota differed between inflamed and non-inflamed mucosa.

After establishing that alterations in the mucosal glycome in healthy and inflammatory profiles are associated with changes in gut microbial communities, we sought to characterize the dynamics of these correlations (structure of glycans-microbiota) in both G1 and G2. Network analysis discriminated, in G2, two strong associations between individual glycans and microbial families, while in G1 no significant correlations were found. At M6, two strong correlations between microbial taxa and two complex N-glycans were found in G2; in contrast, no significant associations were found in G1 (Figures 3A,B).

Closer examination of these correlations showed that bacterial family 1 was positively correlated with glycan X (Figure 3A), while bacterial family 2 was negatively correlated with glycan Y in G2 (Figure 3B). Taken together, these findings support the hypothesis that alterations in host glycosylation may impact gut microbiota composition.

Figure 3 Co-expression network analysis of the correlation of differential microbiome taxa and specific glycan traits at G1 and G2.

A. Network illustrating associations between microbial taxa and glycan X. **B.** Network illustrating associations between microbial taxa and glycan Y. Each node represents each microbiota or individual glycan species. The connecting line represents the existence of correlations between two nodes.

The impact of gut mucosal glycome in shaping the intestinal microbiota composition in CD patients is in line with the mouse data generated within this project (Rodrigues & Gaifem *et al.*, Gut Microbes 2025; [18]). Particularly, we have observed that mice lacking complex branched *N*-glycans (*Mgat5*^{-/-} mice), known to display increased susceptibility to severe colitis, harbour a dysbiotic gut microbiota composition, characterized by a decreased abundance of specific taxa belonging to Firmicutes phylum, such as *Blautia*, *NK4A214* group and *Lachnoclostridium* genera. This is concomitant with the increased abundance of bacterial species such as *Marvinbryantia*, *Ruminococcaceae*, *Clostridia*_UCG 014, *Anaeroplasma*, and *Lachnospiraceae*_FCS020_group were detected in *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice. Additionally, *Muribaculaceae* family from Bacteroidota phylum, *Coriobacteriaceae*_UCG 002, *Eggerthellaceae* from *Actinobacteriota* phylum and *Paracoccus* genus belonging to Proteobacteria phylum, were also found increased in *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice (Figure 4). This supports the pivotal role of gut mucosal glycome in dictating microbial dynamics associated with IBD.

Figure 4 Linear discriminant analysis (LDA) of the gut microbiota composition based on 16S rRNA sequencing in the faecal samples of *Mgat5*^{WT} and *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice.

Data shows the variation of microbial taxa of single-housed (SH) *Mgat5*^{WT} and *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice at steady state. Colours represent the different microbiota according to the phylum level.

3.2 Functional impact of glycome-microbiota associations in CD

To further explore how these microbial taxa may be influenced by the different glycan traits, and taking into consideration that the gut microbiome can utilize glycans as carbon source, we are using PICRUST2 to further infer potential functional impacts of these associations with glycan metabolism and

to investigate the functional pathway enrichment between disease recurrence (G1) and remission (G2). This analysis is still ongoing and will provide us some insights on glycan metabolism via microbiota in health to disease transition.

The gathered data demonstrate that the glycome-microbiota axis is paramount for gut health, diverging in both remission and relapse. We will further take advantage of these data to identify a predictive specific signature associated with remission and/or relapse at M0. To achieve this, we will employ bioinformatic predictive models based on these data. Additionally, taking advantage of a well-characterized inaugural cohort of CD patients (and healthy controls), we will assess this predictive glycome-microbiota signature as a proof-of-concept validation cohort.

Chapter 4

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Chapter 5

Final Remarks

5. Final Remarks

Our results revealed the existence of a glycome-microbiota axis that is distinct from relapse and remission IBD, supporting that alterations in the gut mucosa glycome shape microbiota composition and that even upon surgery (i.e., similar to reset of the intestinal inflammatory environment), the presence of particular glycan traits in the mucosa will impose microbiota alterations, promoting divergent disease outcomes. This will be validated in an inaugural cohort of IBD patients, which will be paramount to assess the impact of glycome in promoting disease via microbiota composition.

